

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ISSUE OF DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract. In this thesis, paying attention to the important aspects of the development of information competence among pedagogues in modern education, he comments on the issue of the development of information competence among primary school teachers.

Key words: Modern education, primary school teacher, information competence, competence, student, education, training, information communication tools.

Introduction

First of all, according to ideas that have a strong place in the science of pedagogy, information competence is considered one of the main competences (from the point of view of its importance for the successful socialization of a person), its presence at the basic level in a graduate of a general education school (or so it is considered - in a student entering a higher education institution) It should be noted that it is considered a necessary condition for the further formation of the information competence of the primary school teacher.

At the basic level of information competence, personality qualities representing a set of knowledge, skills, and valuable attitude to the use of new information technologies and the effective implementation of various forms of information activities in order to solve socially significant tasks that arise in real situations in a person's daily life and in society understood.

The information competence of the teacher serves as the development of the information competence of the school graduate, and reflects a set of valuable attitudes towards the effective implementation of knowledge, skills and various forms of information activity by the pedagogue, as well as the use of new information technologies in professional educational activities, it is understood as a professional and personal quality of a pedagogue. This includes professional knowledge, skills and motivation to implement information activities specific to the teacher, preparation for using new information technologies in the educational process.

The development of information competence among specialists in the field is a very important issue in the current conditions of education. Including, if it is

said that paying attention to the development of basic competence among primary school teachers or developing the information competence of every primary school teacher working in the field of education is one of the necessary conditions for providing modern knowledge to the representatives of the future class, no exaggeration. After all, the increasing acceleration of information communication processes today requires not only the representative of any field, but also the teacher of any subject working in the educational process to have the necessary level of information competence development. Because in practical processes today it is impossible to achieve a sufficient or desired result without the use of information and communication tools.

If teachers do not have a sufficient level of special information competence, that is, competence in the field of using computer technologies in the educational process, and if they are not ready to search for and choose quality software products, to use them appropriately to solve specific didactic tasks, It is natural that new teaching information technologies are useless in primary education. Accordingly, the information competence of a primary school teacher can be structurally expressed in the form of the totality of two blocks: a block of "basic" components of information competence and a block of "special" components.

The teacher's information competence is the introduction of skills related to the implementation of various forms of information activities in order to expand professional outlook and independent education, as well as receiving, processing and assimilating existing information, creating new knowledge and communicating it to the professional community.

What was mentioned above about the main components of the information competence of the future elementary school teacher is directly related to the component composition of the information competence of the graduate of the general education school. Therefore, the teacher's information competence is a guide to the selection of the basic components, and according to its content, the criterion considered as a criterion of conformity can serve, that is, the primary school teacher of each basic component of the information competence of the general education school compliance with the appropriate component of the graduate's information competence and its consideration in the context of professional pedagogical activity.

The emergence of a new element in the pedagogical system, new information technologies change its functions in many ways and allow to achieve new pedagogical results. The use of new information technologies for

teaching significantly increases the professional capabilities of the teacher, expands the limits of his pedagogical competence, and therefore serves to increase the productivity of his professional activity, that is, to improve the quality of education. Consideration of the structure of the teacher's activity on the use of new information technologies in the educational process of primary education through pedagogical models in accordance with the model is considered one of the issues that require great attention.

Summing up from the above, it can be said that the introduction of the information competence complex to educational institutions will be beneficial in all respects. The widespread introduction of these technologies into the educational system will help solve many problems faced by public educational institutions in time. Currently, the teaching of subjects using modern information and communication devices is of great importance. Primary school teachers can make effective progress in developing their students' creative abilities by widely using the possibilities of computer technologies. For this reason, it is important to make a huge contribution to the development of information competence in students at the stages of training future primary school teachers.

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